

NDAC/L0/092
1987 Feb 2

PROPOSED FORMAT AND METHOD OF COMPARISON FOR FAST AND NDAC ATTITUDES

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1. Introduction

The different attitude representations used by FAST and NDAC (choice of basis functions as well as attitude angles) makes it necessary first to sample the representations at suitable intervals, and then to transform the attitude angles to a common system, before any numerical comparison can be made. Because the basis functions used by both consortia are essentially band-limited to frequencies below some 0.01 Hz, it would be sufficient, in principle, to sample the continuous representations at intervals of some ten to hundred seconds. Rate discontinuities in connexion with gas jets do however add high-frequency components and it may be especially interesting to examine the OGAR performance around the firings. The OGAR comparison should therefore be made on a frame-by-frame basis. Probably this is also most easily adapted to the normal output requirements of the different processes.

The following proposal describes one output format for each consortium, and then gives the formulae for converting each set of attitude angles into a common system for comparison. The method of comparison is only sketched, however, as it may depend on what the data actually look like.

Although the proposed formats foresee a 'true attitude' file from each consortium (along with the OGAR estimate), it is of course sufficient if one consortium provides the true data, preferably the one responsible for generating the simulated input data.

2. Tape format (common to FAST and NDAC)

The physical medium is magnetic tape, 1600 bpi, 9 tracks, phase encoded.

No labels are used. The tapes contain formatted data only, with 80 ASCII characters per logical record (no LF or CR at the end of the record).

A physical record (block) contains an integer number of logical records. The maximum blocklength is 14400 characters = 180 logical records. Any blocklength = 80*n bytes, with n = 1 to 180, is thus acceptable. It is recommended that the maximum blocklength is used except for the last block in the file, which may be shorter (no blank records inserted). However, a fixed blocklength (padded with blank records at the end) is also acceptable.

The first block of the first file is not preceded by any label or EOF mark. The files are separated by a single EOF mark. At least two EOF marks follow the last file on the tape. There is no information about the blocklength and the actual number of blocks in a file other than the EOF mark.

The results from processing one RGC (of up to about 5 revolutions) are contained on a single file. The first logical record contains a character string (A20) identifying the source (FAST/NDAC) and type of data (ATTITUDE, TRUE or OGAR). The content of the second logical record (format: A80) is left unspecified. The consortia may insert suitable character strings for further identification of the simulation and/or processing (the date of processing might be a useful item).

The format for the 'true attitude' file (if there is one) is identical to that of the OGAR file. They are distinguished only by the contents of the first (and possibly the second) logical record.

3. Description of logical records

3.1. FAST data

Data for records 3 to 6+NBGJET are taken from the FAST file 'MCL', and for the remaining records from 'ACFRA'. The items are named and defined as in the FAST IF Document (for 'MCL': Version 4, 20/03/86; for 'ACFRA' Version 1, 10/4/86). (Exception: the integer form of the RGC frame count is called IRGCFC.)

record#	content	format
1	'FAST ATTITUDE : OGAR' or: 'FAST ATTITUDE : TRUE'	A20, 60X
2	(unspecified)	A80
3	IDRGC, TIMBEG, TIMEND, ISM, NBT4, NBSTAR, NECLIP, NBGJET	I6, 2F15.8, L2, 4I6, 18)
4	ECLON, ECLA, RLON	3F17.12, 29X
5	ECLIP1(I), I=1,4	4F15.8, 20X
6	ECLIP2(I), I=1,4	4F15.8, 20X
6+JET (JET = 1 to NBGJET)	NUMFRA(JET), TIME(JET)	I6, F13.6, 61X
7+NBGJET+IRGCFC (IRGCFC = 0 to NBT4-1)	IRGCFC, PSI, TETA, PHI	I6, 3F17.12, 23X

Explanations:

IDRGC = RGC identification number (FAST internal)
 TIMBEG = time of the beginning of the first frame [MJJD]
 TIMEND = time of the beginning of the last frame [MJJD]
 ISM = T (true) for nominal, F (false) for redundant SM
 T corresponds to the SM preceding the main grid (TBC)
 NBT4 = number of frames present in the RGC
 NBSTAR = number of stars in the RGC
 NECLIP = number of eclipses (earth and moon): $0 \leq \text{NECLIP} \leq 2$
 NBGJET = number of gas jets: $0 \leq \text{NBGJET} \leq 200$

ECLON = ecliptical longitude of the RGC pole [rad]
 ECLA = ecliptical latitude of the RGC pole [rad]
 RLON = longitude of the origin from the ecliptic node [rad]
 Note: RLON = 0 is expected (TBC)

ECLIP1(1:4) = times (decimal RGC frame counts) for the first eclipse:
 ECLIP1(1) = entering penumbra, $0 \leq \text{ECLIP1} \leq \text{NBT4}$
 ECLIP1(2) = entering umbra, "
 ECLIP1(3) = leaving umbra, "
 ECLIP1(4) = leaving penumbra, "
 For any transition that does not occur in the RGC
 interval, the corresponding time is set = 0

ECLIP2(1:4) = same for the second eclipse

NUMFRA(JET) = frame number for the JETth jet actuation, $\text{JET}=1, \text{NBGJET}$;
 $0 \leq \text{NUMFRA} \leq \text{NBT4}-1$

TIME(JET) = decimal RGC frame count for the centre of the JETth jet;
 $0 \leq \text{TIME} \leq \text{float}(\text{NBT4})$, $\text{NUMFRA} = \text{int}(\text{TIME})$

IRGCFC = integer RGC frame count; $0 \leq \text{IRGCFC} \leq \text{NBT4}-1$
 PSI = first attitude angle at frame mid-time [rad]
 TETA = second attitude angle at frame mid-time [rad]
 PHI = third attitude angle at frame mid-time [rad]
 Frame mid-time is: $\text{RGCF} = \text{float}(\text{IRGCFC}) + 0.5$

Note the definition of attitude angles:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{PSI} &= (\text{PSI})_a + (\text{PHI})_a \\
 \text{TETA} &= (\text{TETA})_e \\
 \text{PHI} &= (\text{PHI})_e
 \end{aligned}$$

The angle PSI does not have to be in a specified interval (such as 0 to 2π), but the absolute value should not exceed 999 rad to avoid format overflow. TETA and PHI are (normally) small angles.

3.2. NDAC data

The contents of the NDAC attitude records are based on the descriptions in the RGO/DSRI interface specification, Issue 2 (Petersen, 1987). The names and definitions of the various data items follow that document.

record#	content	format
1	'NDAC ATTITUDE : OGAR' or: 'NDAC ATTITUDE : TRUE'	A20, 60X
2	(unspecified)	A80
3	IFFNUM, FMTBEG, FMTEND, NRECFL	I6, 2F17.6, I6, 34X
3+IFM (for IFM = 1 to NRECFL)	FMTIME, JFFLAG, RANGLE, RPHASE, SPHASE	F17.6, I3, 3F17.12, 9X

Explanations:

IFFNUM	= frame file number (= 0 for test data)
FMTBEG	= mid-time of first frame, in [s] from J1988.0
FMTEND	= mid-time of last frame, in [s] from J1988.0
NRECFL	= number of frame records; 0 <= NRECFL <= 27000
FMTIME	= frame mid-time in [s] from J1988.0
JFFLAG	= 1 if a jet firing occurred in the frame, otherwise 0
RANGLE	= heliotropic revolving angle [rad]
RPHASE	= heliotropic revolving phase angle [rad]
SPHASE	= heliotropic spin phase angle [rad]

The heliotropic angles are normally in the range 0 to 2π , but this is not a strict requirement as long as their absolute values are ≤ 999 rad

4. Differential attitude angles (a, b, c)

Basically we want to compare the orientations of a certain vector triad [x y z] (the instrument frame) according to different sources or estimators: the 'true' orientation, and the OGAR estimates thereof according to FAST and NDAC. Also during the mission, when we have no 'true' data, we still want to compare FAST versus NDAC. The expected differences are of the order of a fraction of an arcsecond.

Perhaps the simplest way to compare the orientations of the (almost coinciding) triads [x1 y1 z1] and [x2 y2 z2] is by way of the 1-2-3 Euler angles (a, b, c) transforming one triad into the other:

$$[x_2 \ y_2 \ z_2] = [x_1 \ y_1 \ z_1] * A_1(a) * A_2(b) * A_3(c) \quad (1)$$

Here, A1, A2, A3 are the elementary rotations as defined by Lindegren (e.g. NDAC/LO/083). Performing the matrix multiplications and assuming that $|b| < \pi/2$ (in fact, all three angles a, b, c should be very small) we obtain the following rigorous formulae for the Euler angles:

$$a = \text{ATAN2}(-y_1'z_2, \ z_1'z_2) \quad (2a)$$

$$b = \text{ASIN} (x_1'z_2) \quad (2b)$$

$$c = \text{ATAN2}(-x_1'y_2, \ x_1'x_2) \quad (2c)$$

Thus a, b, c can be calculated for any pair of triads, as soon as they have been expressed in the same reference frame (which is necessary for computing the scalar products). The result is of course independent of the reference frame, which can therefore be chosen for convenience.

The angles (a, b, c) signify rotations about the instrument axes x, y, and z. Since the latter nearly coincide with the satellite's principal axes of inertia, they are in a sense a 'natural' description of the attitude differences, at least as long as they remain small.

Note also that if $[x_1 \ y_1 \ z_1]$ is the nominal and $[x_2 \ y_2 \ z_2]$ the actual attitude control reference frame, then (a, b, c) are simply the RTAD angles (ϕ , θ , ψ). This is used in the Annex to check the subroutines.

5. Time collation

The mid-time of the frame with FAST frame count number IRGCFC, expressed on the NDAC time scale (seconds from J1988.0), is computed as:

$$TFRAME = (TIMBEG - 47161.5) * 86400 + T4 * (\text{float}(\text{IRGCFC}) + 0.5) \quad (3)$$

where

$$T4 = (\text{TIMEND} - \text{TIMBEG}) / \text{float}(\text{NBT4} - 1) * 86400 \quad [\text{s}] \quad (4)$$

is the mean frame period (the non-linearity over 12 h can be neglected for our purposes). Collating TFRAME frame-by-frame with the NDAC equivalent FMTIME is a safe way of checking that the frames match and that the time scales are correctly interpreted. The comparisons below should be made only for matching frames: $\text{abs}(TFRAME - FMTIME) < \text{TEPS}$ (a few microseconds?).

6. Conversion to a common reference frame

The ecliptical frame J2000.0 is the most convenient common frame for the orientations of the FAST and NDAC instrument triads. This section gives the explicit formulae for $K'[x \ y \ z]$ (the ecliptical components of the instrument triad) in terms of the FAST and NDAC attitude angles.

6.1. Ecliptical components of the FAST triad

The basic equations are contained in NDAC/LO/083. That document however made use of the true angle $(\text{PSI})_e$ in the Euler 3-2-1 representation, whereas the angle actually obtained by the OGAR process is the 'broken' angle $\text{PSI} = (\text{PSI})_a + (\text{PHI})_a$ from the astronomical 3-1-3 representation. The difference is a second-order quantity in the (small) angles TETA and PHI. The true Euler angle is recovered by the rigorous formula:

$$PSIE = PSI + \text{atan}(\sin(PHI) * \sin(TETA) / (\cos(PHI) + \cos(TETA))) \quad (5)$$

Combining eqs (083.4) and (083.7) we find

$$K'[x \ y \ z] = A3(ECLON + \pi/2) * A1(\pi/2 - ECLA) * A3(PSIE) * A2(TETA) * A1(PHI) \quad (6)$$

The columns of this 3x3 matrix contain the ecliptical components of the x, y, and z axes. It may be computed by the subroutine ECZF (Annex).

6.2. Ecliptical components of the NDAC triad

The basic equations are again found in NDAC/LO/083. With SLON denoting the longitude of the nominal sun (at time FMTIME), we find from (083.6) and (083.8)

$$K'[x \ y \ z] = A3(SLON) * A1(RPHASE - \pi/2) * A2(\pi/2 - RANGLE) * A1(SPHASE) \quad (7)$$

This 3x3 matrix may be computed by the subroutine ECZN (Annex).

7. Comparisons

Assuming that both parties provide the true and OGAR attitudes in their respective representations, we may compute four attitude matrices, e.g.

ZMATTF = K'[x y z] for the true attitude according to FAST
 ZMATTN = K'[x y z] for the true attitude according to NDAC
 ZMATOF = K'[x y z] for the OGAR attitude according to FAST
 ZMATON = K'[x y z] for the OGAR attitude according to NDAC

The first two should in principle be the same. Any two matrices may be compared according to section 4 and the differential angles (a, b, c) calculated by means of the subroutine ZCOMP (Annex). Each comparison might produce a table of the following quantities:

IRGCFC = integer RGC frame count (0 to NBT4-1)
 JFFLAG = 1 for a jet actuation, 0 other wise
 SPHASE = heliotropic spin phase: this determines the solar torques
 a, b, c = attitude difference angles

The analysis of these data might include plots of (a, b, c) versus frame number and/or spin phase, and simple summary statistics (mean, rms, and extreme values). The behaviour around the jet actuations might be shown by the plots or by special statistics.

The proposed formats do not yet include any provision to list the transits actually used in the attitude determination.

ANNEX: Subroutines for calculating and comparing attitude matrices

SUBROUTINE zcomp : calculates the differential angles (a, b, c)

SUBROUTINE eczf : calculates K'[x y z] from FAST attitude angles (calls 'rotate')

SUBROUTINE eczn : calculates K'[x y z] from NDAC attitude angles (calls 'rotate' and 'slong')

SUBROUTINE rotate : general routine for triad rotation

REAL*8 FUNCTION slong : calculates the longitude of the nominal sun

The main program (attcom) illustrates the use of zcomp, eczf, and eczn by means of the numerical example in NDAC/LO/083. The resulting output is listed after the program.

```

c=====
c      PROGRAM attcom
c=====
c
c Test program for subroutines ZCOMP, ECZF, ECZN
c L Lindegren 1987 Feb 04
c
c      IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c      DIMENSION zmat0(3,3), zmatf(3,3), zmatn(3,3)
c
c Time and RGC :
c
c      t      = 86400d3
c      eclon  = 3.90d0
c      eclat  = 0.35d0
c      rlon   = 0d0
c
c Nominal attitude --> zmat0 :
c
c      rpha0 = 0.5245575761d0
c      rang0 = 0.7504915784d0
c      spha0 = 2.4639297917d0
c      CALL eczn(t, rpha0, rang0, spha0, zmat0)
c      WRITE(*, '(/"Nominal ecliptical [x y z]:", (/3f20.16))') zmat0
c
c Actual attitude according to FAST --> zmatf :
c Cpsi = (PSI)a + (PHI)a below corresponds to (PSI)e = -0.27652116093
c
c      psi    = -0.2765087310d0
c      teta   = -0.0054158705d0
c      phi    = 0.0045901399d0
c      CALL eczf(eclon, eclat, rlon, psi, teta, phi, zmatf)
c      WRITE(*, '(/"FAST/RTAD ecliptical [x y z]:", (/3f20.16))') zmatf
c
c Actual attitude according to NDAC --> zmatn :
c
c      rpha  = 0.5233959239d0

```

```

rang = 0.7484437196d0
spha = 2.4673791370d0
CALL eczn(t, rpha, rang, spha, zmatn)
WRITE(*, '(/"NDAC/RTAD ecliptical [x y z]:", (/3f20.16))') zmatn

```

Comparisons:

```

CALL zcomp(zmat0, zmatf, a, b, c)
WRITE(*, '(/"Difference FAST/RTAD - Nominal:"/3f20.16)') a,b,c

```

```

CALL zcomp(zmat0, zmatn, a, b, c)
WRITE(*, '(/"Difference NDAC/RTAD - Nominal:"/3f20.16)') a,b,c

```

```

CALL zcomp(zmatf, zmatn, a, b, c)
WRITE(*, '(/"Difference NDAC/RTAD - FAST/RTAD:"/3f20.16)') a,b,c

```

END

```

*****
SUBROUTINE zcomp(zmat1, zmat2, a, b, c)
*****

```

Compares the orientation of two (nearly coinciding) vector triads

INPUT: zmat1(1:3,1:3) = first vector triad, expressed in some reference frame (the first column contains the direction cosines of the first vector, etc)

zmat2(1:3,1:3) = second vector triad, expressed in the same reference frame

OUTPUT: a, b, c = the Eulerian 1-2-3 angles transforming the first triad into the second, i.e.:
 $zmat2 = zmat1 * A1(a) * A2(b) * A3(c)$

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```

IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
DIMENSION zmat1(3,3), zmat2(3,3)

```

```

xx = 0d0
xy = 0d0
xz = 0d0
yz = 0d0
zz = 0d0

```

```

DO 10 i = 1, 3
  xx = xx + zmat1(i,1)*zmat2(i,1)
  xy = xy + zmat1(i,1)*zmat2(i,2)
  xz = xz + zmat1(i,1)*zmat2(i,3)
  yz = yz + zmat1(i,2)*zmat2(i,3)
  zz = zz + zmat1(i,3)*zmat2(i,3)

```

10 CONTINUE

```

a = datan2(-yz, zz)
b = dasin(xz)
c = datan2(-xy, xx)

```

```

c
c      RETURN
c      END
c*****
c      SUBROUTINE eczf(eclon, eclat, rlon, psi, teta, phi, zmatf)
c*****
c
c      Calculate the matrix K'[x y z] from FAST attitude angles and RGC pole
c
c      INPUT:  eclon      = ecliptical longitude of RGC pole      [rad]
c             eclat      = ecliptical latitude of RGC pole       [rad]
c             rlon       = longitude of origin from ascending node [rad]
c             psi        = first attitude angle = (PSI)a + (PHI)a  [rad]
c             teta       = second attitude angle = (TETA)e        [rad]
c             phi        = third attitude angle = (PHI)e          [rad]
c
c      OUTPUT: zmatf(1:3,1:3) = K'[x y z] = ecliptical components of the
c                    instrument axes x, y, z
c
c      L Lindegren 1987 Feb 03
c
c      IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c      DIMENSION zmatf(3,3)
c      PARAMETER (pi = 3.14159265358979324d0, pihalf = pi/2d0)
c
c      psie = psi+datan(dsin(phi)*dsin(teta)/(dcos(phi) + doos(teta)))
c
c      CALL rotate(zmatf, -3, eclon+pihalf, zmatf)
c      CALL rotate(zmatf, 1, pihalf-eclat, zmatf)
c      CALL rotate(zmatf, 3, psie+rlon, zmatf)
c      CALL rotate(zmatf, 2, teta, zmatf)
c      CALL rotate(zmatf, 1, phi, zmatf)
c
c      RETURN
c      END
c*****
c      SUBROUTINE eczn(t, rphase, rangle, sphase, zmatn)
c*****
c
c      Calculate the matrix K'[x y z] from NDAC attitude angles and the time
c
c      INPUT:  t          = time in seconds from J1988.0          [s]
c             rphase     = heliotropic revolving phase           [rad]
c             rangle     = heliotropic revolving angle           [rad]
c             sphase     = heliotropic spin phase                [rad]
c
c      OUTPUT: zmatn(1:3,1:3) = K'[x y z] = ecliptical components of the
c                    instrument axes x, y, z
c
c      L Lindegren 1987 Feb 03
c
c      IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c      DIMENSION zmatn(3,3)
c      PARAMETER (pi = 3.14159265358979324d0, pihalf = pi/2d0)
c
c      slon = slong(t)

```

```

CALL rotate(zmatn, -3, slon,          zmatn)
CALL rotate(zmatn,  1, rphase-pihalf, zmatn)
CALL rotate(zmatn,  2, pihalf-angle,  zmatn)
CALL rotate(zmatn,  3, sphase,        zmatn)

o
RETURN
END
o*****
o      SUBROUTINE rotate(a, n, angle,  b)
o*****
o
o  HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - elementary rotation matrix
o
o  Performs an elementary rotation of (3,3)-matrix a about the n:th
o  axis, yielding matrix b.  If n < 0, then a is taken
o  to be the identity matrix.
o
o  Input:
o    a    = original (3,3)-matrix (need not be defined if n < 0)
o    n    = rotation axis (taken negative for a = identity matrix)
o    angle = rotation angle [rad]
o
o  Output:
o    b    = matrix after rotation
o
o  NOTE:  a and b may be the same matrix, e.g.
o         CALL rotate(a2, -2, theta,  a2)
o         returns the elementary matrix
o
o         ( cos(theta)  0  sin(theta) )
o         a2 = (      0    1    0      )
o         ( -sin(theta)  0  cos(theta) )
o
o
o  L Lindegren  1984 July 24
o  Corrected   1986 June 4
o
o  IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
o  DIMENSION a(3,3), b(3,3)
o  IF (n .LT. 0) THEN
o    DO 2 i = 1, 3
o      DO 1 j = 1, 3
o        a(i,j) = 0d0
o  1    CONTINUE
o      a(i,i) = 1d0
o  2  CONTINUE
o  ENDIF
o
o  c = dcos(angle)
o  s = dsin(angle)
o
o  nabs = iabs(n)
o  IF (nabs .EQ. 1) THEN
o    DO 10 i = 1, 3
o      p = c*a(i,2) + s*a(i,3)
o      b(i,3) = c*a(i,3) - s*a(i,2)
o      b(i,2) = p

```

```

        b(i,1) = a(i,1)
10    CONTINUE
    ELSE IF (nabs .EQ. 2) THEN
        DO 20 i = 1, 3
            p = c*a(i,3) + s*a(i,1)
            b(i,1) = c*a(i,1) - s*a(i,3)
            b(i,3) = p
            b(i,2) = a(i,2)
20    CONTINUE
    ELSE IF (nabs .EQ. 3) THEN
        DO 30 i = 1, 3
            p = c*a(i,1) + s*a(i,2)
            b(i,2) = c*a(i,2) - s*a(i,1)
            b(i,1) = p
            b(i,3) = a(i,3)
30    CONTINUE
    ENDIF
c
    RETURN
    END
c*****
c      REAL*8 FUNCTION slong(t)
c*****
c
c  HIPPARCOS - General routines - Nominal solar longitude
c
c  This subroutine calculates the nominal solar longitude to be
c  used in conjunction with the heliotropic angles.
c
c  INPUT:
c    t          = time in seconds from the origin epoch of the
c                nominal attitude (J1988.0)
c
c  OUTPUT:
c    slong      = longitude of the nominal sun                [rad]
c                (NOT taken modulo 2*pi!)
c
c  L. Lindegren 1987 Jan 14
c
c      IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)
c      PARAMETER (alon0 = -1.38691d0,   dalon = 0.0172021240d0,
c                ,   g0 = -0.04114d0,   dg = 0.0172019696d0,
c                ,   e = 0.016714d0,   e1 = 2d0*e,   e2 = 1.25d0*e**2)
c
c  The parameter dt0 is the time difference (in [s]) to be added to the
c  NDAC time scale in order to get the time scale on which the nominal
c  scanning law is based:
c
c      PARAMETER (dt0 = 0d0)
c
c      d = (t + dt0)/86400d0
c      alon = alon0 + dalon*d
c      g     = g0 + dg*d
c      slong = alon + e1*d*sin(g) + e2*d*sin(2d0*g)
c
c      RETURN
c      END

```

Nominal ecliptical [x y z]:

.5896295949337751	-.7655853626326689	-.2573246845929029
-------------------	--------------------	--------------------

.4269184712437084	.0249695487754039	.9039453194440954
-------------------	-------------------	-------------------

-.6856220239236535	-.6428495735057755	.3415653175518197
--------------------	--------------------	-------------------

FAST/RTAD ecliptical [x y z]:

.5899787706621531	-.7662277498271713	-.2545978899416965
-------------------	--------------------	--------------------

.4240825097013368	.0257403673853167	.9052576751689457
-------------------	-------------------	-------------------

-.6870801082358522	-.6420533224597927	.3401300574558962
--------------------	--------------------	-------------------

NDAC/RTAD ecliptical [x y z]:

.5899787708340754	-.7662277497001451	-.2545978899255948
-------------------	--------------------	--------------------

.4240825096979254	.0257403675017029	.9052576751672345
-------------------	-------------------	-------------------

-.6870801080903319	-.6420533226067202	.3401300574725034
--------------------	--------------------	-------------------

Difference FAST/RTAD - Nominal:

.0019000000347391	-.0011000001785074	.0026000003257736
-------------------	--------------------	-------------------

Difference NDAC/RTAD - Nominal:

.0018999999612699	-.0010999999844922	.0026000004164480
-------------------	--------------------	-------------------

Difference NDAC/RTAD - FAST/RTAD:

-.0000000000729644	.0000000001942056	.0000000000907552
--------------------	-------------------	-------------------